

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WODAJO****FIRST NAME: AYCHEW TEFETA****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6A****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the primary purpose of the dissertation concept paper, as described in the guide?

- To explore a potential dissertation topic and obtain early feedback from the supervisory committee.¹**
- To present the final findings of the research.
- To replace the dissertation prospectus entirely.
- To fulfill university formatting requirements.

¹ James P. Sampson, Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017). 9.

2. Which of the following is a key factor contributing to successful dissertation research, according to the guide?
- Limiting communication with the major professor.
 - Using complex statistical methods exclusively.
 - Visualizing success and maintaining motivation.**²
 - Avoiding collaboration with other researchers.
3. What is the primary purpose of a style guide in academic writing?
- To enforce strict grammatical rules without exceptions.
 - To replace the need for referencing sources.
 - To limit creativity in writing by standardizing all content.
 - To document consistent approaches to elements like formatting, citations, and terminology.**³
4. Which of the following is a key strategy to avoid plagiarism?
- Using synonyms without citing the original source.
 - Properly citing the author or source of borrowed information.**⁴
 - Copying text verbatim but changing the font style.
 - Paraphrasing without altering the original sentence structure.

² Sampson, Jr. 15.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024). 41.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Kabiru. 34.

5. Which of the following is a defining feature of qualitative research?
- Focuses on numerical data and statistical analysis.
 - Seeks to test hypotheses through controlled experiments.
 - Aims to generalize findings to a larger population.
 - Emphasizes thick description and understanding phenomena in context.**⁵
6. What is the primary purpose of reflexivity in qualitative research?
- To acknowledge and critically examine the researcher's impact on the research process.**⁶
 - To eliminate all researcher bias and achieve complete objectivity.
 - To ensure statistical validity of the findings.
 - To standardize data collection procedures across studies.
7. Which of the following best describes the significance of engaging with primary sources in academic research?
- They summarize existing interpretations, making research faster and easier.
 - They are only useful for historical research and have little relevance in scientific studies.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019). 144-145.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe. 152–154.

- They provide firsthand evidence that allows researchers to develop independent analyses.**⁷
- They eliminate the need for secondary sources, as they contain all necessary information.
8. What is the primary purpose of a research problem in academic writing?
- To summarize existing knowledge without challenging established ideas.
- To prove that the researcher already has the correct answer before conducting research.
- To provide a clear and structured question that guides the research process.**⁸
- To focus only on personal opinions rather than scholarly evidence.
9. Which of the following is the correct way to cite a paragraph from Article 3 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) in a legal text?
- Article 3, paragraph 1.
- Article 3(1).**⁹
- Article 3, section 1.
- Article 3.1.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018). 36.

⁸ Turabian. 29.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (European Commission, 2021). 12.

10. When translating the name of a German ministry into English for an EU document, which approach is most appropriate if the ministry plays a significant role in the text?

- Leave the original name untranslated (e.g., Bundesministerium für Gesundheit).
- Use an ad-hoc translation (e.g., Federal Ministry of Health).
- Use an informal description (e.g., the German health ministry).
- Provide the original name with a translation in brackets (e.g.,**

Bundesministerium für Gesundheit [Federal Ministry of Health]).¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

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¹⁰ European Commission. 30.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.